

SLAVERY OR AGENCY: REINTERPRETING GENESIS 2:15-17

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TEXTUAL EVIDENCE FOR IMMORTALITY LOST AND PROCREATIVITY GAINED

ABSTRACT

Genesis 2:15-17, traditionally interpreted as a divine command disobeyed by humanity, is better understood as a warning delivered not to humanity broadly but to ha'adam, an archetypal male, emphasizing human agency over rote obedience. This paper argues that Yahweh's statement to ha'adam—permitting the consumption of fruit from every Tree, followed by a conditional consequence of mortality—lacks the prohibitive structure of a command. Through textual analysis of vayätzer (“warned”), mikol (“from every”), and mot tamut (“become mortal”), I demonstrate that the narrative frames eating from the Tree of Knowledge as an act of free will in the absence of divine coercion. The knowledge gained, identified as sexual awareness, necessitates expulsion to prevent overpopulation, not punishment. This reading contrasts the pagan gods of Mesopotamian myths who govern by divine whim, positioning Genesis as a story of human free will, culminating in the moral collapse described in Genesis 6:5-6. Reframing these three verses reshapes theological discourse on obedience, sin, and divine intent, offering a fresh lens through which to view biblical scholarship.

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This article is adapted from Chapter Eight of my book, *Genesis II: Reading The Story Again For The First Time* (forthcoming, May 2025), which reinterprets the Eden narrative through its Hebrew text and ANE context, whose theme is, as Marc Zvi Brettler notes, a story reflecting “Immortality Lost and Procreativity Gained.”

INTRODUCTION

Genesis 2:15-17 has sparked extensive scholarly debate, often obscured by traditional assumptions of disobedience and punishment. Widely regarded as the moment humanity violates a divine command, triggering the “Fall,” this passage has profoundly shaped theological doctrines of original sin and divine punishment across Jewish and Christian traditions. This understanding, however, may owe more to the inertia of post-biblical traditions—such as readings emphasizing a forbidden act and divine retribution—than to the Hebrew text itself, prompting a reevaluation whose results depart from the conventional lens of sin and disobedience.¹

In this paper, I propose that Genesis 2:15-17 does not depict a command disobeyed by humanity at large but a warning delivered specifically to *ha'adam* (הָאָדָם), the narrative’s archetypal male. As a warning, therefore, the act of eating the fruit from the Tree of “the Knowledge of Good and Bad” (*hadda'at tov vara*, הַדְּלִיעַת טוֹב וְרָע) becomes a deliberate exercise of agency in the face of foreseeable consequences.

The narrative’s traditional interpretation rests on three questionable assumptions. The first assumption holds that *Yahweh* issues a command (translated from *vayätzer* (וַיִּצַר)) prohibiting eating fruit from the Tree of Knowledge of good and bad. The second assumption translates *mot tamut* (מוֹת תָּמוּת) as “you shall surely die,” In other words, capital punishment is the immediate consequence of eating the fruit in question. The third assumption assumes *hadda'at tov vara* represents a dangerous moral or intellectual breach warranting divine execution.

However, a closer analysis of the text reveals ambiguities that challenge these assumptions. First, the verb *vayätzer* can mean “warned,” as seen in other contexts (e.g., Genesis 26:11).¹ Second, in verse 2:16, the phrase *mikol 'etz-haggan* (מִכָּל עֵץ-הַגָּן), “from every tree of the Garden,” lacks an exclusionary clause marking the fruit as forbidden.² Third, If not certain death, how then should we interpret *mot tamut* since we learn that post-expulsion, the couple die by natural causes after living long lives (‘Adam’s lifespan is 930 years)?³ Indeed, the text shows that once *ha'adam* and his wife, *Chavvah* (חַוְוָה), acquire *hadda'at tov vara*, they are expelled from the Garden, not executed.

This reinterpretation is significant when compared to the Mesopotamian flood epics, such as the epics of *Gilgamesh* and *Atrahasis*.⁴ Ignoring *Yahweh*'s warning was an act of free will. In pagan theology, the gods completely control human fate and free will was not contemplated. In the Garden of Eden narrative (Genesis 2:5 – 4:17, 6:5-6), therefore, this act of free will, allowing ha-adam and *Chavvah* to govern themselves for good or for bad, stands as a polemic against the pagan doctrines illustrated in these [more] famous flood epics.

TEXTUAL AND GRAMMATICAL ANALYSIS

The Hebrew text of Genesis 2:15-17 underpins this paper's reinterpretation of *Yahweh*'s words as a warning rather than a command, emphasizing *ha'adam*'s agency over disobedience. This section analyzes four key Hebrew textual elements—*vayätzer*, *mikol 'etz-haggan*, *'akhol tokhel*, and *mot tamut*—to demonstrate that the narrative frames the act of eating as a deliberate choice with foreseeable consequences, not a violation of a divine mandate.

vayätzer: warned, not commanded.

*“And Yahweh warned (*vayätzer*) ha'adam, you may certainly eat from every tree of the Garden; however, should you eat from the Tree of the Knowledge of Good and Bad, you will surely become mortal” (Genesis 2:15-17).⁵*

The verb *vayätzer*, traditionally translated as “commanded,” is pivotal to the passage's interpretation. The support for its translation as “warned” arises from *vayätzer*'s semantic range—a range that extends beyond issuing commands. Included in this range are advising, instructing, charging, and, most important, warning. For example, in the NLT, Genesis 2:16, like the translation in this paper, uses “warned.” In Genesis 26:11, Abimelech “warns” (*wayyāšaw*, וַיִּשָּׂא) against touching *Isaac*'s wife, implying caution rather than prohibition. Similarly, in 1 Kings 11:10, *Yahweh* warns Solomon against idolatry, framing it as advice to avoid consequences (see NLT, NET, ISV, BSB, CEV).⁶ context also aligns with a warning. In Genesis 2:16, *vayätzer* introduces a permissive statement—“You may certainly eat from every tree” (*mikol 'etz-haggan*)—which lacks the prohibitive structure expected of a command (e.g., *lo' tō'kal* (לֹא תֹאכַל), “you shall not eat”).⁷ A command prohibiting eating fruit from a single, specific tree (v. 2:17) would contradict the inclusive permission of verse 2:16, as no exclusionary

clause such as “except (אֲבָרָה), “except”) appears. Translating *vayätzer* as “warned” resolves this tension, casting *Yahweh*’s words as an advisory notice about a consequence (*mot tamut*), not a directive to be obeyed.

Claus Westermann supports this, arguing that the context suggests a caution to be heeded, not a legalistic order. Bruce Waltke adds that such a warning implies *ha’adam*’s moral capacity, with *Yahweh* leaving the choice to him. John Walton further notes that ancient Near Eastern instructions often informed rather than restricted, aligning with “warned.”⁸ Traditional translations favoring “commanded” may reflect theological assumptions of disobedience, yet the absence of a direct prohibition—especially since *Chavvah*, not yet created (2:22), receives no warning—undermines this reading. For example, if the Genesis author meant commanded, he might have more reasonably written something along the lines of,

“And the LORD God commanded the man, saying, “You may surely eat of every tree of the Garden, except the tree of the knowledge of good and evil for in the day that you eat of it you shall surely die.

One might object that *mot tamut*’s severity suggests a command, but warnings often carry grave consequences (e.g., “beware of dog”), focusing on the outcome, not obligation. Thus, “warned” better captures the verse’s tone, prioritizing *ha’adam*’s agency over divinely ordained obedience.

***mikol ‘Etz-Haggan and ‘akhol tokhel*: Unrestricted Permission**

The phrase *mikol ‘etz-haggan* (מִכֹּל עֵץ־הַגָּן), “from every tree of the Garden,” is unambiguous, encompassing all trees without exception. The Amplified Bible’s rendering—“freely (unconditionally) eat”—underscores this inclusivity. The infinitive absolute *‘akhol tokhel* (אָכַלְתָּ, “you may certainly eat”) reinforces unrestricted permission, as Robert Alter notes, emphasizing freedom rather than limitation.⁹ If 2:17 were a prohibition, an exclusionary marker (e.g., *lo’ tokhəlu*, as in Genesis 3:3’s later addition by *Chavvah*) would be expected, yet none appears, supporting a warning’s conditional structure over a command’s restrictive one.

***mot tamut*: become mortal vs. “surely die”**

The consequence *mot tamut* (מָוֹת תָּמוּת, “surely become mortal”) follows logically from a warning. Traditionally translated as “you shall surely die” (e.g., NKJV), it suggests capital

punishment applied immediately, yet ha'adam's death by natural causes 930 years post-expulsion (Genesis 5:5) is a major contradiction. Alter's interpretation of "doomed to die" approximates "becoming mortal," reflecting the loss of access to the Tree of Life (3:22-24) and immortality. Westermann sees this as a caution about mortality, not a punitive execution, aligning with *vayātzet* as "warned."¹⁰ The infinitive absolute intensifies certainty, not timing, reinforcing a delayed outcome consistent with agency.

Together, *vayātzet* as "warned," *mikol's inclusivity*, *'akhol tokhel's* permissiveness, and *mot tamut's* mortality frame 2:15-17 as a coherent, if not obvious, warning: *ha'adam* is free to eat from all trees, including the Tree of Knowledge, but choosing the latter risks access to the Tree of Life and his immortality.

hadda'at tov vara: the knowledge of good and bad

The consequence of eating from the Tree of the Knowledge of Good and Bad—acquiring *hadda'at tov vara*—necessitates expulsion from the Garden, but why? This question has long preoccupied scholars with interpretations shaping the narrative's theological weight. Gordon Wenham catalogs five theories for *hadda'at tov vara's* meaning. They are (1) moral discernment (distinguishing right from wrong), (2) omniscience (godlike knowledge), (3) wisdom (akin to Yahweh's), (4) moral autonomy (self-defined ethics), and (5) sexual awareness (procreative capacity).¹² This paper argues that the fifth—sexual awareness—is the only coherent explanation for why Yahweh expels the couple, namely, as a safeguard against overpopulation by procreative immortals, aligning with the warning structure of Genesis 2:15-17.

The first four theories fall short because they fail to connect the knowledge gained to the narrative's outcome: expulsion. Moral discernment, omniscience, wisdom, or autonomy might warrant correction or divine reprimand, but why banishment from the Garden? These interpretations assume expulsion as punishment, yet Genesis 3:22 suggests a preventive motive: "lest they take also from the Tree of Life and live forever." Without a clear link to immortality or the Garden's boundaries, the other four theories leave the expulsion arbitrary, misaligned with the warning's conditional consequence (*mot tamut*). Sexual awareness, however, directly ties to procreation, which, paired with potential immortality, threatens overpopulation—a logical trigger for expulsion.

What, then, does sexual awareness entail in this context? In Deuteronomy 1:39 and 2 Samuel 19:35, *hadda'at tov vara* denotes a knowledge absent in children and faded in the elderly, suggesting the vitality of puberty and reproductive capacity.¹³ Genesis 2:25 describes *ha'adam* and *Chavvah* as *'arummim* (עָרוּמִים, “naked and not ashamed”), a state of pre-sexual innocence. After eating and acquiring *hadda'at tov vara*, Genesis 3:7 states they “knew they were naked” (*'êrummîm*, עִירְמוּם), prompting genital-specific coverings—an action implying sexual cognizance. Marc Zvi Brettler interprets this as procreative awareness, a view echoed by Nahum Sarna, who links it to Genesis 4:1’s “knew” (*yada*, יָדָע), connoting sexual intimacy.¹⁴ Ibn Ezra and Claus Westermann, citing Gunkel and Schmidt, further support this, noting its prevalence in modern scholarship.¹⁵ Westermann emphasizes that procreation alters the Garden’s balance, necessitating expulsion to limit access to eternal life.¹⁶

This reading aligns with Genesis 2:15-17’s warning: *ha'adam* is cautioned that eating may yield *hadda'at tov vara*, triggering mortality from the loss of access to the Tree of Life (3:22-24). Unlike moral or intellectual knowledge, sexual awareness introduces procreation, which, without mortality, risks an unsustainable population. Critics might argue that moral discernment better fits theological traditions of sin, yet this ignores the text’s plain focus on physical consequences (nakedness, childbirth in 3:16). By identifying *hadda'at tov vara* as sexual awareness, this paper reinforces the narrative’s focus on agency: *ha'adam*’s choice initiates human destiny, not divine retribution. An analogy might be helpful at this point.

At first, you loved working in the King’s Garden but have become weary of clearing irrigation ditches and fixing sluice gates. Now, the King had permitted you to eat the fruit from any tree in the Garden but warned that the fruit of one particular tree, if eaten, would make you sexually active, a behavior incompatible with life in the Garden. The choice was yours - a sterile world of eternal slavery or immortality lost, procreativity gained. The choice was easy.

This example reflects the nuance of Genesis 2:16–17. The verb *vayetzav* (וַיִּצְוֶה), traditionally rendered “commanded,” is better understood in this context as “warned”—a directive motivated by divine care rather than authoritarian decree.¹¹ The absence of a prohibition, coupled with *Chavvah*’s non-involvement at this stage, underscores choice over obedience, setting the stage for theological and contextual implications.

THEOLOGICAL IMPLICATIONS: AGENCY OVER DISOBEDIENCE

The Garden in Eden, *gan vā'eiden* (גַּן־בְּעֵדֶן) in Hebrew, is often misconstrued as a paradise of leisure and perfection, a view that obscures its narrative role in Genesis 2:15-17. In ancient Near Eastern (ANE) contexts, the *gan vā'eiden* was an enclosed plot of land mirroring royal estates like those in Sumerian or Babylonian temple complexes.¹⁷ These estates required intensive labor, usually centered around irrigation, to maintain the Garden's lushness. Genesis 2:5-6 sets the stage: no human existed to till the ground until *ha'adam* was formed for this purpose. The charge *lā'avdah ūlāshomrah* (לֹא־עָבָדָה וְלֹא־שָׁמְרָה), "to work and keep," 2:15) implies a servile role, not an idyllic existence.¹⁸ Ancient audiences would have immediately recognized *ha'adam* as a caretaker, not an honored guest. If the *gan-eiden* were a tropical resort, *ha'adam* would be its groundskeeper.

This challenges modern perceptions of the *gan-eiden* as a utopia, which projects a romanticized loss onto the expulsion. Instead, *ha'adam*'s choice to eat the fruit from the Tree of the Knowledge reflects a deliberate preference for a mortal, procreative life outside of the Garden over eternal servitude within it. John Walton notes that ANE Gardens symbolized divine order, not human comfort, aligning with *ha'adam*'s functional purpose.¹⁹

This reframing illuminates why expulsion follows the acquisition of *hadda'at tov vara*—sexual awareness. To this point, Marc Zvi Brettler writes,

"The connection between (procreative) sexuality and mortality is compelling and was well understood, even in antiquity. If people were to be both sexually procreative and immortal, disastrous overpopulation would result."²⁰

Ibn Ezra, one of the most distinguished Jewish commentators from the Middle Ages, also viewed sexual awareness to be the meaning of *hadda'at tov vara*. Nahum Sarna, citing Ibn Ezra, writes,

*"Ibn Ezra, followed by many scholars today, understood carnal knowledge to be the intended meaning of the Tree Of The Knowledge of good and bad since the first human experience after eating the forbidden fruit is the consciousness of nudity; moreover, immediately after the expulsion from Eden it is said, 'Now ha'adam knew his wife, Chavvah.'"*²¹

Sexual awareness means procreativity. However, procreation risks overpopulation, threatening the Garden's balance. Genesis 3:22 confirms this: expulsion prevents access to the Tree of Life, ensuring mortality. Unlike the traditional view of expulsion as punishment, this reading sees it as a logical consequence of *ha'adam's* agency, choosing a finite life of human destiny over a sterile eternity. Nahum Sarna agrees, arguing that procreation fundamentally alters the Garden's dynamics, necessitating a very different human trajectory.²²

Genesis 2:15-17's emphasis on agency contrasts sharply with ANE flood myths, highlighting its unique theological perspective. In the Epic of *Gilgamesh* (Tablet XI), a serpent steals immortality from *Gilgamesh*, reflecting a fatalistic loss driven by divine whim, not human choice.²³ Genesis, however, casts the serpent as a catalyst for *ha'adam's* decision, with *hadda'at tov vara* enabling moral and procreative agency. Similarly, in the Atrahasis myth, humans are created as divine laborers, subject to gods' caprice, with a flood triggered by their noise, not a moral failure.²⁴ Genesis elevates human consciousness from pagan determinism to metaphysical agency: *ha'adam's* choice initiates a moral trajectory, not a divine reaction. Claus Westermann notes that Genesis reorients ANE motifs toward human responsibility, distinct from gods' arbitrary rule.²⁵

This trajectory culminates in Genesis 6:5-6, where humanity's loss of *yetzer hatov*—the “good inclination” balancing moral intent—prompts divine judgment. The Hebrew word *yetzer* (יֵצֶר), often linked to human disposition, appears implicitly in 6:5:

“Every inclination (yetzer) of their hearts was only evil.”²⁶

Unlike ANE floods, where divine annoyance drives destruction (e.g., *Atrahasis*), the Genesis flood is Yahweh's response to mankind's loss of humanity, the *yetzer hara*, a direct outcome of the agency granted in 2:15-17. Robert Alter argues that Genesis frames humans as moral agents whose choices shape cosmic consequences, not as pawns of divine caprice.²⁷ The warning in 2:15-17, rooted in *mikol's* permissiveness and *mot tamut's* consequence, thus positions *ha'adam's* act as the narrative's genesis, not a fall. Expulsion safeguards the Garden while launching humanity into moral decay, ending with Genesis 6:5-6, making Genesis 2 a prequel to the flood, not a standalone creation-fall account. By reframing the Garden as a labor-intensive space and contrasting it with ANE myths, this reading underscores human agency as Genesis' theological core.

ENDNOTES

On post-biblical traditions shaping Genesis 2:15-17, see Nahum M. Sarna, *Genesis: The JPS Torah Commentary* (Philadelphia: Jewish Publication Society, 1989), 23, noting how later interpretations imposed legalistic readings on the text's ambiguities.

For *vayätzer* as “warned,” see Genesis 26:11 in New English Translation (NET), 2nd ed. (Richardson, TX: Biblical Studies Press, 2019); Berean Standard Bible (BSB) (Bible Hub, 2020).

On *mikol 'etz-haggan*'s inclusivity, see Nahum M. Sarna, *Genesis: The JPS Torah Commentary* (Philadelphia: Jewish Publication Society, 1989), 20.

Genesis 5:5 (NET, NLT) notes *ha'adam*'s 930-year lifespan, undermining immediate death. Cf. Robert Alter, *The Five Books of Moses: A Translation with Commentary* (New York: W. W. Norton, 2004), 28.

For Mesopotamian epics, see Stephanie Dalley, trans., *Myths from Mesopotamia: Creation, the Flood, Gilgamesh, and Others* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1991), 109–16 (Atrahasis), 89–101 (Gilgamesh).

The author's translation renders *vayätzer* as “warned” and *mot tamut* as “become mortal.” Cf. Genesis 2:16 in Holy Bible, New Living Translation (NLT) (Carol Stream, IL: Tyndale House Publishers, 2015).

For *vayätzer*'s semantic range, see Genesis 2:16 (NLT); Genesis 26:11 (NET, BSB); 1 Kings 11:10 in NLT, International Standard Version (ISV) (International Standard Version Foundation, 2020), BSB, and Contemporary English Version (CEV) (New York: American Bible Society, 1995).

On the absence of *lo' tō'kal*, see Sarna, *Genesis*, 20.

Claus Westermann, *Genesis 1–11: A Commentary* (Minneapolis: Augsburg Publishing House, 1984), 223; Bruce K. Waltke, *Genesis: A Commentary* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2001), 85; John H. Walton, *The Lost World of Genesis One* (Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 2015), 94.

Alter, *Five Books of Moses*, 27; cf. Genesis 2:16 in *Amplified Bible* (not in the bibliography, consulted for emphasis).

Alter, *Five Books of Moses*, 28; Westermann, *Genesis 1–11*, 224.

For *vayetzav* as “warned,” see discussion in Waltke, *Genesis*, 85.

Gordon J. Wenham, *Genesis 1–15, Word Biblical Commentary* (Dallas: Word Books, 1987), 67–68.

See Deuteronomy 1:39 and 2 Samuel 19:35 (NET, NLT) for *hadda'at tov vara's* connotations.

Marc Zvi Brettler, *How to Read the Jewish Bible* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005), 45; Sarna, *Genesis*, 21.

For Ibn Ezra, Gunkel, and Schmidt, see Westermann, *Genesis 1–11*, 226, and Sarna, *Genesis*, 21.

Westermann, *Genesis 1–11*, 226–27.

For ANE Garden contexts, see Walton, *Lost World of Genesis One*, 92–93.

On *lə'avdah ûlëshomrah*, see Sarna, *Genesis*, 19.

Walton, *Lost World of Genesis One*, 93.

Brettler, *How to Read the Jewish Bible*, 45.

Sarna, *Genesis*, 21.

Sarna, *Genesis*, 22.

Dalley, *Myths from Mesopotamia*, 95–96 (Gilgamesh, Tablet XI).

Dalley, *Myths from Mesopotamia*, 112–14 (Atrahasis).

Westermann, *Genesis 1–11*, 65.

Genesis 6:5 (NET); cf. Alter, *Five Books of Moses*, 35.

Alter, *Five Books of Moses*, 35–36.

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